

AMYLOLYTIC PROPERTIES OF FUNGI ASSOCIATED WITH SPOILAGE IN BREAD

Okoko, F.J and Ogbomo, O.
Microbiology Department, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Amylolytic properties of the fungi associated with the spoilage of bread in Abraka was investigated. Bread samples were collected from various bakeries in the town and exposed for 14 days at different locations and observed daily for spoilage. The three organisms found to be associated with the spoilage of bread were *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Rhizopus stolonifer*. The amylolytic properties of the fungi isolated were tested using the effects of starch concentration, incubation time, assay temperature and pH. For starch concentration, the activity was 3.5mg/l at 5% and 0.0mg/l at 0% for *Rhizopus stolonifer*. For incubation time, amylase activity was 1.6mg/l at 96h and later dropped to 0.7mg/l at 144h. for *Rhizopus stolonifer*. For assay temperature, the amylase activity was 2.9mg/l at 30°C at 30% and later dropped to 0.5mg/l at 45°C while for the pH, the amylase activity was 3.9mg/l at pH 6 and 2.4mg/l at pH 5 and this varies with increase or decrease in pH. These trends were observed in all organisms used for this study.

INTRODUCTION

Enzymes are a class of proteins which catalyze chemical reactions (Chapman *et al*, 1975). They could also be defined as a protein catalyst that have average specificity for the reaction catalyzed and the molecule of the substrate. The active molecules are called the substrate and substances formed are called the products.

Enzymes activity is affected by factors such as substrate concentration, temperature and pH. The rate of enzyme catalyzed reaction increases with substrate concentration. Enzyme also changes activity with change in pH if the pH deviates greatly from the optimum. Temperature also effects the enzyme for if the temperature is too high above the optimum, enzyme is denatured. (Prescott *et al*, 1999).

Many enzymes consist of protein and also a microprotein compound. The apoenzyme is the protein component and the non protein component is called the cofactor. The complete enzyme consisting of both the apoenzyme and the cofactor is called the holoenzyme.

Fungi are a group of thallophytes lacking chlorophyll and true roots. They live heterotrophic mode of life either as parasites or saprophytes (Dutta, 2001). They reproduce sexually or asexually. They are defined as eukaryotic since they possess membrane bound nuclei. They are spore bearing because the amylase activity was 4.0mg/l at 30°C and later dropped to 2.0mg/l at 45°C for *Aspergillus niger*. This trend was observed in other organisms used in this study. The effect of pH on amylase activity in the test organisms showed that the activity was 4.0 at pH6, 2.2 and 1.8 at pH 5 for *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Rhizopus stolonifer* respectively.

They undergo sexual reproduction which is common mode of reproduction in many fungi. The various forms of fungi spores are: Basidiospore, Ascospore, Sporangiospore and Chlamydospore.

Fungi are used in so many industrial processes including baking and fermentation (Pitt and Hocking, 1985). They digest and break down molecules into successive smaller units until they are absorbed into the organism. Carbohydrates are present in at least small quantities in most foods but the chief sources are sugars and starches (Boons, 2001). Amylase is the digestive enzyme needed to digest carbohydrates.

Fungi have an optimum temperature for enzyme production. It has been reported that the optimum temperature for best yield of enzyme by a strain *Aspergillus niger* is 29°C±0.5°C (Childyal *et al*, 1981). Fungal amylase could be a major contributor to the spoilage of food such as bread by fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus stolonifer* and *Aspergillus Flavus*. These fungi have been isolated from various spoiled bread (Hopkins *et al*, 1942).

Water requirements for microorganisms are often related to the water activity (A_w) in the environment. Water activity is defined as the ratio of the water vapour pressure of food suitable to the ratio of vapour pressure of pure water at the same temperature. It has been reported that the optimal water activity for some bread spoilage fungi are: 0.98 for *Aspergillus niger* and 0.99 for *Rhizopus* (Christein, 1980). Fungal growth in food can be prevented by reducing the water activity to 0.85, this inhibits *Aspergillus* species.

Some bacteria involved in bread spoilage are lactic acid bacteria, *Lactobacillus mesenteroides*, *Bacillus* sp etc.

The growth of fungi on bread is a substrate saprophyte relationship with the bread providing nourishment and the fungi surviving on it as long as favourable environmental conditions prevail.

Enzyme synthesis by fungi has been considered by a number of workers and a number of these organisms such as *Humicola insolens* (Cooney and Emerson, 1964), *Populasporea thermophila* (Chapman *et al*, 1975), have been reported to produce extracellular amylase. However, more information is still needed on enzyme production by fungi with respect to the temperature requirement and pH which are the information this work is designed to provide.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Samples

Bread samples for this study were bought from stores located in different parts of Abraka town.

They were placed in different locations and exposed for 10 days and observed daily for spoilage. The spoilt portions of the bread were scraped and stored in sterile cellophane bags and saved in the refrigerator for further studies.

Isolation Procedure

The working desk was wiped with alcohol soaked cotton wool to ensure an aseptic working surface.

One gram of scraping from the bread was weighted into a 250ml beaker into which was added 100ml distilled water to form a suspension.

Ten sterile test tubes were placed in a test tube rack and ten-fold dilution of the suspension was made using the sterile pipettes.

From tubes 10^{-2} , 10^{-4} and 10^{-6} , 1ml of each dilution was transferred into sterile petridishes in triplicate, using a sterile pipette. A bottle of sterile agar was taken from a water bath adjusted to 45°C and poured into the sterile petridishes to about two thirds of the depth of each dish. The dishes were well labeled and left undisturbed on the bench to set. They were inverted and incubated at room temperature for 15 days to obtain pure culture. Each of the dilution was subcultured and pure colonies of isolates were stored on agar slant and placed in the refrigerator.

Identification of Organisms

A sterile inoculating needle was used to pick a small piece of the fungal mycelia and placed on a clean grease free slide. A drop of lactophenol was applied on the slide and covered with a cover slip. The slide was viewed under the microscope using a x40 objective. The organisms were identified by their morphology making use of the standard identification manual.

Reagents Used

The reagents used in this study, are Dinotrosalicylic Acid Reagent (DNSA) which was prepared by dissolving 1g dinitrosalicylic, 20g of potassium nitrate and 20ml of 2N sodium hydroxide in 100ml distilled water.

The yeast extract medium was prepared by dissolving 1% soluble starch in 0.02m phosphate buffer at pH 6.9.

ENZYME ASSAY

Effect of starch concentration on Amylase synthesis

The yeast extract medium prepared earlier was reconstituted into concentrations of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0% in triplicate. Twenty milliliter from each concentration was dispensed into different sterile universal bottles, labeled and incubated at 121°C for 15min. Each of the bottles was inoculated with the test organism and incubated at 30°C for 6 days. Following incubation the content of each bottle was filtered using a glass funnel fitted with Whatman NO. 1 England filter paper and the amylase activity of each filtrate was determined by adding 1ml of fungus filtrate to 1ml assay medium and allow to stand for 1h. One milliliter of dinitrosalicylic acid reagent was added to 1ml of the filtrate-starch-reaction mixture and its transmittance determined by using the Carnspec M105 Spectrophotometer.

Effect of Incubation time on Enzyme Activity

The inoculated media were filtered at various hours, (48h, 72, 96, 120 and 144h) following incubation after which the filtrates were assayed for enzyme production using the method of Bernifield (1957). The filtrate containing crude enzyme was placed in an ice bath to prevent denaturation of the enzyme.

One milliliter of the fungus filtrate was incubated with 1ml of the assay medium and left at 30°C for 1h. Filtrate of the non-inoculated control were also obtained and similarly assayed. One milliliter of dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) reagent was added to 1ml of the filtrate-starch mixture to estimate reducing sugars. Transmittance at 540nm was determined using a camspec M105 spectrophotometer.

The filtrate-starch reaction mixture of the non-inoculated control was also treated with DNSA and used to set transmittance at 100%. The results were reported in amylase units. One amylase unit is the amount of enzyme in 1ml of filtrate which releases 1mg of reducing sugar from 1% starch solution in one hour at 30°C at pH 6.8. The mean of three replicate determination was taken in each case.

The transmittance of 1ml samples of known standard aqueous-glucose solution of 0.125, 0.25, 1.0 and 2.0mg/ml was determined and its transmittance was read and used to construct a curve of percent transmittance as related to mg of glucose per ml.

Effect of Assay Temperature on Amylase Activity

The starch yeast medium which was prepared earlier and stored in sterile tubes were inoculated with the different test fungi and incubated at 30°C for 6 days. This was followed by filtration and amylase activity of the filtrates was determined for 30°C, 35°C, 40°C and 45°C (Temperatures). One milliliter of the fungus filtrate and 1ml of the assay medium was incubated for 1h at each of the above temperatures.

One milliliter of denitrosalicylic acid reagent was added to 1ml of the filtrate-starch-reaction mixture and its transmittance was determined at 540nm using a Campsec M105 spectrophotometer. All samples were used in triplicate.

Effect of pH on Amylase Activity

The starch yeast extract store in sterile bottles for this study were inoculated with test fungi and labeled. They were incubated at 30°C for 6 days. 1% soluble starch was prepared and divided into five portions for amylase assay. The pH was adjusted to 3,4,5,6, respectively.

Amylase activity was determined by incubating 1ml of the fungus filtrate with 1ml of each solution at for 30°C for 1h. 1ml DNSA was added to 1ml filtrate-starch-reaction mixture and the transmittance determined at 540nm using a Campsec M105 spectrophotometer. All samples were prepared in triplicate.

RESULTS

The results showed that the fungi isolated from the bread used in this study are *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Rhizopus stolonifer*.

Effect of Starch Concentration on Amylase Synthesis

The results were shown that, the optimum amylase activity was exhibited by *Rhizopus stolonifer* (3.5mg/l) at 5% substrate concentration, this is followed by *Aspergillus niger* (3.1mg/l) and *Aspergillus flavus* (2.8mg/l) at pH5

respectively. The minimum amylase activity was observed in *Rhizopus stolonifer* which showed no activity at 0%. *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus niger* showed activity of (0.1mg/l) and (0.2mg/l) respectively.

For the three organisms used in this study the amylase activity was highest (3.5mg/l) at 5% concentration and later dropped to 0.0. at 1% for *Rhizopus stolonifer*, 0.1 for *Aspergillus flavus* and 0.2 for *Aspergillus nige* as shown in figure 1.

Effects of incubation time on amylase activity

The results showed that *Aspergillus niger* exhibited the optimum amylase activity of (1.6mg/l), this was followed by *Rhizopus stolonifer* (1.4mg/l) and *Aspergillus flavus* (1.3 mg/l) respectively at 96 hours. The minimum amylase activity was recorded by *Aspergillus flavus* (0.5mg/l), followed by *Aspergillus niger* (0.7mg/l) and *Rhizopus stolonifer* (0.8mg/l) respectively at 144 hours.

The amylase activity was highest at 96 hours and lowest at 144 hours in all the organisms used in this study as shown in figure 2.

Effects of Temperature on Amylase Activity

The result of the effects of temperature showed that the optimum amylase activity was inhibited by *Aspergillus niger* (3.9mg/l), followed by *Aspergillus flavus* (3.5mg/l) and *Rhizopus stolonifer* (2.8mg/l) respectively at a temperature of 30°C.

The minimum amylase activity was recorded by *Rhizopus stolonifer* and *Aspergillus niger* (0.5mg/l) at 45°C. (Figure 3).

Effects of pH on Amylase Activity

The result showed that *Rhizopus stolonifer* showed the highest activity (3.9mg/l) at pH 6. *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus niger* showed amylase activity of 2.4 and 1.8 respectively at pH 5. The minimum amylase activity was observed at pH 3 in all the test organisms as shown in figure 4.

DISCUSSION

The results showed the fungi involved in bread spoilage in this study were *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizopus stolonifer*.

The effects of incubation time, pH, starch concentration and temperature on the amylase production was investigated in these fungi. The amylase activity was found to be 3.9, 3.5 and 2.8 at 30°C for *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Rhizopus stolonifer* respectively. The activity was observed to decrease with an increase in temperature.

Extra cellular amylase activity was observed to increase as the concentration of starch in the medium increased. Amylase activity was observed to be highest in *Aspergillus niger* at 1% starch concentration. It was also observed to decrease with decrease in starch concentration. No amylase activity was observed in *Rhizopus stolonifer* at 0% starch concentration. This was in line with the work of Chapman *et al* (1975) who reported on starch utilization and extracellular amylase synthesis in *Populaspora thermophila*.

Amylase activity was found to be highest at pH 6 in *Rhizopus stolonifer*, closely followed *Aspergillus flavus* at pH 5. Any increase or decrease in those pH (5 and 6) would cause a decrease in amylase activity. This trend was observed in all the three organisms in this study.

Fig1: Effect of Starch Concentration of Amylase Synthesis

Fig 2: Effect of Incubation Time on Amylase activity

Fig 3: effect of Assay Temperature on Amylase Activity

Fig 4: Effect of pH on Amylase Activity

CONCLUSION

Many studies in recent past have shown the medical and economic importance of fungi. This study has shown *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Rhizopus stolonifer* as been responsible for the spoilage of bread. Their saprophytic mode of life may be one of the qualities that has conferred this destructive property on these organisms. This is because many of them have the ability to elicit some very potent enzyme into their substrates.

The three fungi isolated in this study are capable of secreting the enzyme amylase into the bread which is one of the factors responsible for bread spoilage. It is therefore recommended that we avoid the exposure of our foods and other valuable materials to fungi and their spores as a means of protecting them from spoilage and damage.

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Received for Publication: 29/10/09

Accepted for Publication: 10/02/10